

Quantitative Treatment of the Variation of Relative Apparent Molal Heat Contents in Dilute "Strong Electrolyte" Solutions According to Cube-root of Concentration

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The expression for κ (kappa) of the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes has been modified in previous publications. The expression for κ_m , the modified kappa, includes the effective ionic diameter, a , which occurs in the denominator along with D , the dielectric constant and T , the absolute temperature. It follows from theory that in the concentration range of a solution in which a remains constant, κ_m should vary according to cube root of concentration, C . Equations have been deduced containing κ_m to account for the variation of relative apparent molal heat contents in dilute "strong electrolyte" solutions when their concentrations are varied. The equations have been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on NaCl, KCl, KNO₃, NaOH, HCl, BaCl₂, and Li₂SO₄ so far and have been found satisfactory.

ON the basis of thermodynamic principles the following equations have been deduced¹.

$$\bar{L}_2 = \bar{H}_2 - \bar{H}_2^0 = -\nu RT^2 \left[\frac{d \ln f}{dT} \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$= \phi_L + n_2 \frac{\delta \phi_L}{\delta n_2} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{and the heat of dilution } \Delta H_D = -\phi_L \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\phi_L = \phi_H - \phi_H^0$

In the aforesaid equations $\bar{L}_2$ and ϕ_L represent respectively the relative partial molal heat contents and relative apparent molal heat contents in dilute strong electrolyte solutions, f the mean activity coefficient of the ions, n_2 the number of solute moles per n_1 moles of solvent in the solutions and the other symbols have their usual significance.

Application of Debye-Hückel theory² for very dilute solutions of strong electrolytes to equation (1) yields the following expression,

$$\bar{L}_2 = S_{(H)} \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (4)$$

At a constant temperature $S_{(H)}$ is constant and can be calculated from theory¹. It also follows from equations (2) and (4) that

$$\phi_L = 2/3 S_{(H)} \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (5)$$

It has been pointed out in previous publications³⁻⁵ that the expression for κ in the Debye-Hückel theory should be modified. For a 1:1 strong electrolyte at 25° we may write $\kappa = \beta \sqrt{C}$ and the modified kappa, $\kappa_m = \beta (1.22/\sqrt{a}) C^{1/3}$, where $\beta = 0.329 \times 10^8$ at 25°.

The modification of κ necessitates corresponding changes in the expressions for $\bar{L}_2$ and ϕ_L recorded above and they may be effected in the following way. For a 1:1 strong electrolyte equation (4) may be written as :

$$\bar{L}_2 = (S_{(H)} \beta \sqrt{C}) / \beta = S_{(H)} \kappa / \beta \quad \dots (4a)$$

Now replacing κ by κ_m in equation (4a) and making proper adjustments we may write

$$\bar{L}_2 = (S_m \kappa_m) / \beta = S_m (1.22/\sqrt{a}) [C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}] \quad \dots (4b)$$

where C_0 represents that concentration at which $\bar{L}_2 = 0$ and $S_{(H)}$ has been replaced by S_m , since it is now a function of the effective ionic diameter a also, in addition to those mentioned in standard books¹.

The modified expression for ϕ_L may be written as follows by combining equations (4b) and (2) ;

$$\phi_L = (3/4) S_m (1.22/\sqrt{a}) [C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}] \quad \dots (5a)$$

$$= S [C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}]$$

$$\text{where } S = (3/4) S_m (1.22/\sqrt{a}) \quad \dots (5b)$$

$$= S (C)^{1/3} - \phi_H^0, \text{ where } \phi_H^0 = S (C_0)^{1/3} \quad \dots (5c)$$

It may be mentioned that C_0 of (5a) is different from C_0 of (4b).

As already stated, equations (4b) and (5c) should hold good for very dilute solutions. For relatively more concentrated solutions it has been found necessary to add to them fresh terms containing C and higher powers of C . The equation for ϕ_L applicable to relatively high concentrations may then be written as follows

$$\phi_L = S(C)^{1/3} - \phi_H^0 + \alpha C + \beta C^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

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For a given electrolyte, S and ϕ_H^0 each retains its value intact in the equations (5c) and (6) above $C=0.001 M$.

Young and Seligmann⁶ have proposed the following equation

$$\phi_x = S^0 \sqrt{C} + (\frac{1}{2}B)C + (1/3C') C^{3/2} \quad \dots (7)$$

where S^0 , B and C' are constants at a given temperature and $S^0 = (2/3)S_{(H)}$ and so can be calculated from theory. They have subjected equation (7) to test using a large number of 1:1 and 2:1 electrolytes and have found it satisfactory up to $\sqrt{C}=0.2$ in most of the cases investigated.

In this paper equations (5c) and (6) have been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on a number of 1:1 and 2:1 strong electrolytes in aqueous solutions.

It is to be noted that the equations for the 1:1 and 2:1 strong electrolytes have the same form but the constants in them differ, for example, the value of S for a 2:1 electrolyte is much higher than that for a 1:1 electrolyte. It may also be mentioned that S can be calculated from theory for each electrolyte, provided its effective ionic diameter, a , is known and its dependence on temperature over the desired range is also known.

In a previous publication⁷, it has been shown on the basis of the data on equivalent conductance that the hydration of the ions of KNO_3 , $AgNO_3$, $NaCl$, KCl and HCl increases markedly at or below $0.001 N$. Consequently the effective ionic diameter, a , of each of them changes and this brings about a change in the values of S and ϕ_H^0 in equation (5c) below $0.001 N$. This will be evident from the data recorded in Table 2.

Processing of the data and verification of the equations :

The data, collected from Table (8-12-1A), appendix A, p. 707 of Harned and Owen's book¹, are recorded in Tables 1, 2 and 3 of this paper. Under the head miscellaneous are mentioned the electrolytes, the equations used and the values of the constants in them. In the second column, C represents the initial concentration of the electrolyte selected in moles/liter.

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Tables 1 and 3 that above $C=0.001 M$, the agreement between the values of ϕ_x observed and those calculated by using equation (5c) is fairly satisfactory up to $0.02 M$ for $CsCl$, $0.04 M$ for $NaCl$ and KCl , $0.06 M$ for $NaOH$ and $0.02 M$ and $0.01 M$ for Li_2SO_4 and $BaCl_2$, respectively. Using the values of ϕ_H^0 and S recorded in Table 1 in the concentration range above $0.001 M$, equation (5c) is not applicable to solutions of HCl and KNO_3 . However, for very dilute solutions, below $0.001 M$, it applies to all the electrolytes listed in Table 2 and

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ϕ_x IN 1:1 ELECTROLYTE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values		
		Observed	Calcd. Eqn. (5c)	Calcd. Eqn. (6)
NaCl	0.0004	8.5	8.1	8.1
Eqn. (5c)	0.0016	17.0	17.4	17.5
$\phi_H^0 = 7.8$	0.0036	25	25.3	25.3
$S = 216$	0.0064	33	32.3	32.3
Eqn. (6)	0.01	40	38.7	38.7
$\alpha = 0$	0.0225	55	53.2	52.9
$\beta = -500$	0.04	67	66.1	65.3
$\phi_H^0 = 7.8$	0.0625	77	77.8	76.0
$S = 216$	0.09	83	89.0	84.9
KCl	0.0004	8.5	7.7	7.7
Eqn. (5c)	0.0016	16.0	16.9	16.9
$\phi_H^0 = 8.0$	0.0036	24	24.6	24.6
$S = 213$	0.0064	31	31.5	31.5
Eqn. (6)	0.01	38	39.0	37.8
$\alpha = 0$	0.0225	54	52.1	51.5
$\beta = -1240$	0.04	65	64.8	62.9
$\phi_H^0 = 8.0$	0.0625	72	76.5	71.7
$S = 213$	0.09	77		77.4
CsCl	0.0004	8.0	8.0	8.0
Eqn. (5c)	0.0016	15	15.4	15.4
$\phi_H^0 = 4.7$	0.0036	21	21.7	21.6
$S = 172$	0.0064	27	27.2	27.1
Eqn. (6)	0.01	32	32.4	32.0
$\alpha = 0$	0.0225	43	44.9	43.4
$\beta = -3000$	0.04	49	—	49.3
$\phi_H^0 = +4.7$	0.0625	51	—	51.9
$S = 172$	0.09	51		49.3
NaOH	0.0004	9.5	8.4	8.4
Eqn. (5c)	0.0016	19	19.3	19.3
$\phi_H^0 = +10.2$	0.0036	28	28.4	28.4
$S = 252$	0.0064	36	36.6	36.6
Eqn. (6)	0.01	44	44.1	44.1
$\phi_H^0 = +10.2$	0.0225	62	61.9	61.7
$\alpha = 0$	0.04	77	76.0	75.5
$S = 252$	0.0625	90	89.8	88.6
$\beta = -300$	0.09	99	102.7	100.3
HCl	0.0004	9.6		8.0
Eqn. (6)	0.0016	19.2		19.7
$\phi_H^0 = +11.7$	0.0036	29		29.8
$S = 264$	0.0064	38		39.2
$\alpha = 300$	0.01	48		48.2
$\beta = 0$	0.0225	71		69.6
	0.04	93		90.6
	0.0625	114		111.9
	0.03	134		133.6
KNO_3	0.0004	8.0		7.5
Eqn. (6)	0.0016	15.1		15.2
$\phi_H^0 = +8.0$	0.0036	20.0		19.6
$S = 218$	0.0064	23		23.3
$\alpha = -1440$	0.01	24		24.7
$\beta = 1300$	0.0225	22		21.8
	0.04	12		11.2
	0.0625	-6		-6.4
	0.09	-29		-29.4

in the case of KNO_3 , it holds good up to $C=0.0036 M$.

As already stated, the low values of S and ϕ_H^0 in equation (5c) recorded in Table 2 are to be attributed to a marked increase in the hydration of the ions⁷ of the electrolytes used at or below $0.001 M$.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ϕ_L IN VERY DILUTE SOLUTIONS OF 1 : 1 AND 2 : 1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values	
		Observed	Calcd. Eqn. (5c)
NaCl	0.0001	4.5	4.5
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	8.5	8.6
$\phi_H^0 = +2.3$	0.0016	17.0	14.9
S = 147			
KCl	0.0001	4.5	4.5
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	8.5	8.6
$\phi_H^0 = +2.3$	0.0016	16.0	14.9
S = 147			
CsCl	0.0001	4.0	4.0
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	8.0	8.1
$\phi_H^0 = +2.8$	0.0016	15.0	14.4
S = 147			
NaOH	0.0001	4.8	4.8
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	9.5	9.5
$\phi_H^0 = +3.25$	0.0016	19.0	17.0
S = 173			
HCl	0.0001	4.8	4.8
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	9.6	9.7
$\phi_H^0 = +3.3$	0.0016	19.2	17.2
S = 176			
KNO ₃	0.0001	4.1	4.2
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	8.0	8.3
$\phi_H^0 = +2.8$	0.0016	15.1	14.8
S = 150	0.0036	20.0	20.2
BaCl ₂	0.0001	23.8	23.2
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	46.0	46.0
$\phi_H^0 = +16.1$	0.0016	86.0	82.4
S = 842			
Li ₂ SO ₄	0.0001	24.0	24.0
Eqn. (5c)	0.0004	47.0	47.0
$\phi_H^0 = +15.34$	0.0016	91.0	83.6
S = 846			

The data recorded in Table 1 and 3 also show that equation (6) holds good for all the electrolytes used in the concentration range 0.001 M to 0.09 M.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ϕ_L IN SOLUTIONS OF 2 : 1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values		
		Observed	Calcd. Eqn. (5c)	Calcd. Eqn. (6)
BaCl ₂	0.0004	46		
Eqn. (5c)	0.0016	86	86.8	86.9
$\phi_H^0 = +39.5$	0.0036	124	126.0	126.2
S = 1080	0.0064	160	161.1	161.5
Eqn. (6)	0.01	194	193.1	193.6
$\alpha = 100$	0.0225	268	265.4	265.1
$\beta = -5000$	0.04	329	329.9	325.9
$\phi_H^0 = 39.5$	0.0625	375	389.0	375.8
S = 1080	0.09	412		412.1
Li ₂ SO ₄	0.0004	47		
Eqn. (5c)	0.0016	91	89.3	89.3
$\phi_H^0 = +62.7$	0.0036	135	136.4	136.4
S = 1300	0.0064	177	178.7	178.7
Eqn. (6)	0.01	218	217.3	217
$\alpha = 0$	0.0225	307	304.3	302.4
$\beta = -3900$	0.04	377	381.9	375.7
$\phi_H^0 = 62.7$	0.0625	438	—	438.0
S = 1300	0.09	488		488.1

It may, therefore, be concluded that for very dilute solutions of the strong electrolytes listed, as predicted by equation (5c), ϕ_L varies as cube root of the concentration C and that application of equation (5c) may be extended to relatively more concentrated solutions, generally up to 0.02 M in many cases, provided the values of the constants ϕ_H^0 and S, which it contains, are properly selected.

References

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